

Big O notation, algorithm evaluation method

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Annotation

This article discusses Big O notation, which is widely used in evaluating algorithms. Big O notation assesses the efficiency of any algorithm based on its execution time as well as memory consumption.

Keywords

Big O, algorithm, function, binary search, constant function, linear function, exponential function, quadratic function

Big O notation is a function that defines the level of complexity of the algorithm as well as its limit. The main goal is to characterize how much the value of a function increases as its argument increases. Imagine that we have a function

$$T(n) = 4n^2 - 2n + 2.$$

like this:

The smallest value of the functions is 2, and its value will only increase. As the value of the Argument N approaches infinity, the last free term and the term whose coefficient is equal to 2 can be ignored as they do not have impact on function's value. Therefore, in the case of Big O notation, this function is equivalent to the following value:

Because the rest of the components have the ability to grow very slowly

$$T(n) = O(n^2)$$

compared to the square of N. From this it follows that the fastest growing

component is taken into account in terms of the O notation. Algorithms are also evaluated in this way. Let us say that you have a simple linear search algorithm, function $F(N)$. N is the length of these array elements, and in the linear search algorithm, all elements are examined and as many elements are considered as the value increases. So the execution time of the algorithm changes like a linear function respectively. In the Binary search algorithm, the situation is different. The algorithm decomposes an array with N elements recursively into two, repeating it until the smallest elements remain. Simply put, if the array contains 8 elements, a recursion is executed three times. This can be easily calculated on the basis of a logarithm with base 2: $\log_2(8) = 3$. So the time of the algorithm is equal to the number of its walks, while the binary search algorithm on Big O is executed in $\log(N)$ time!

Considering that the addition (merge) sorting algorithm also works recursively by dividing the array by two and comparing the last two elements, and remembering that there is a one-time addition Action for each division, it means: the algorithm performs a $\log(N)$ action to break up into two, as well as an N action to add. More generally the algorithm is executed in $O(N \cdot \log(N))$ time. This is its time indicator, which is now in the Saras of very fast algorithms. But his memory, which we have assessed the effectiveness of $o(n)$ and this is very very slow for large amounts of information is considered to occupy memory.

Algorithms can be classified through Big O, but since the execution time of algorithms depends on the processor and similar devices, they never estimate how long it could take to execute some algorithm in time units.

References

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